

WHY ELIMINATION OF PORCINE REPRODUCTIVE AND RESPIRATORY SYNDROME (PRRS) IN SLOVENE FARMS FAILED?

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SUMMARY: Slovenia was free of PRRS before joining European Union (EU) in 2004. In EU quarantine for animals coming from other EU members is not mandatory and thus quarantine-free import of pigs from EU member countries unfortunately worsened the health status of pigs in our country. This is how diseases were and still are introduced in Slovenia. Antibodies against PRRS were detected in Slovene domestic pigs already in the second half of the year 2004. In 2010 as part of monitoring and in 2011 according to the annual Order the status of PRRS in Slovenia had been re-established. In both studies the PRRS antibody prevalence was 48% and results from molecular epidemiology originating from the same monitoring detected high genetic diversity which revealed the circulation of numerous subtypes all belonging to genotype 1. And in year 2012 genotype 2 was detected for the first time. Regarding these data both the quarantines and biosecurity measures were not implemented in farms. The study was carried out on 24 (5 negative, 19 positive) farms to evaluate the implementation of required biosecurity measures. On the positive farms for the elimination of PRRS either natural exposure or serum inoculation and strict biosecurity measures were proposed. On the negative farms only biosecurity measures were proposed. Five of the negative farms kept the negative status as a result of the implementation of all the proposed biosecurity measures. In seven positive farms PRRS was eliminated, all these farms adopted the strict biosecurity protocol. In 12 farms neither external nor internal biosecurity measures were implemented at all or at least not to a satisfying level. Hence PRRS and probably also other diseases were easily spreading between the farms and also inside the farms. Main detected deficiencies in biosecurity measures in Slovene farms are: introducing new pigs without quarantine, different categories of pigs in the same room, no consistency with all in all out system, outside traffic in the yard, numerous outside visitors to the farm. Slovenia was not aware of its excellent health status before EU membership and did not take measures to gain the official PRRS-free status which would definitely result in the economic benefits. Now

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economic status in pig breeding will not improve without well planned and well thought-out action.

Key words: *biosecurity, PRRS, control*

INTRODUCTION

Porcine reproductive and respiratory syndrome (PRRS) is an economically significant swine disease worldwide. The total cost of productivity losses due to PRRS virus (PRRSV) in the US national breeding and growing-pig herd was estimated at US \$ 664 million annually (Holtkamp et al., 2013). The mean loss per outbreak in Europe is 126 €/sow and total PRRS cost of an infected European farm is around 100 €/sow/year (Nieuwenhuis et al., 2012). Slovenia was free of PRRS before joining European Union (EU) in 2004 (Valenčak, 2004). In EU quarantine for animals coming from EU members is not mandatory and thus quarantine-free import of pigs from EU member countries unfortunately worsened the health status of pigs in our country. This is how the PRRS and other diseases were and still are introduced in Slovenia.

The highest density of the domestic pig population is located in the eastern part of the country. Moreover, the majority of the Slovenian pig industry involved traditional small pig farms. Antibodies against PRRS were detected in Slovene domestic pigs already in the second half of the year 2004. In 2010 as part of monitoring and in 2011 according to the annual Order the status of PRRS in Slovenia had been re-established. In both studies the PRRS antibody prevalence was around 48% and results from molecular epidemiology originating from the same monitoring detected high genetic diversity which revealed the circulation of numerous subtypes all belonging to genotype 1 (Toplak et al., 2010). And in year 2012 genotype 2 was detected for the first time. Regarding these data both the quarantines and biosecurity measures were not implemented in Slovene farms.

There is no drug to stop PRRS virus replication in the host. Therefore, pig herds need to adopt strict biosecurity programs (Pitkin et al., 2009; Spronk et al., 2010) to prevent PRRS virus infection. Once infected, the options are: to keep the farm PRRSV positive and control the manifestation of clinical disease or to eliminate PRRSV from the farm. To eradicate PRRS from a pig farm, there are different strategies including: complete herd depopulation and repopulation with PRRSV-negative pigs (Dee, 2003), test and removal (Dee and Molitor, 1998), and immunisation either with herd closure (Torremorell et al., 2003) or vaccination or serum inoculation and partial depopulation (Dee et al., 1997a; Dee et al., 1997b).

Implementation of biosecurity measures is essential for successful control or elimination of PRRS. Biosecurity is the term used to describe the measures and procedures needed to protect a population against the introduction and spread of pathogens. A biosecurity plan can be implemented to attain two strategic objectives:

- external biosecurity: policies developed to prevent the introduction of a new pathogen to the farm
- internal biosecurity: a biosecurity strategy developed to reduce the spread of disease among pigs on the farm (Pitkin et al., 2009).

External biosecurity includes: new replacement or incoming stock should be negative, quarantine, transportation of animals with clean, disinfected and dry transport vehicles, minimize or ban visitors to the farm, mandatory shower and changing of clothes and boots. Recent research has demonstrated the ability of infectious PRRSV to be transmitted by aerosols over a distance of 120 meters. However, preliminary results from experimental studies along with field reports indicate that aerosol transmission of PRRSV can occur at least up to 3.3 km or more (Dee et al. 2005, Otake et al., 2010). To reduce the risk of airborne spread of PRRSV, the adaptation of filtration systems to swine facilities has come about. Installation of an air filtration system depends upon the individual producer's budget, the location of the site (high swine density vs. low density), the level of acceptable risk and type of production system (Otake et al., 2010; Reicks, 2010).

In order to prevent spreading the virus it is essential to know the routes of spreading the virus. Pigs can be infected either by direct contact or indirectly by animal products, biological vectors, by contaminated materials or in a contaminated environment.

1. Direct routes

As stated, pigs are the only animal capable of becoming infected with PRRSV (Zimmerman et al., 1997). Once infection occurs, the virus can be shed from persistently infected pigs via blood, saliva, milk and colostrum, urine and feces, as well as contaminated semen (Rossow et al., 1994; Wills et al., 1997).

1.1 Live pigs

To prevent introduction of virus with live animals the following biosecurity measures have to be implemented:

- replacement stock should originate from PRRS negative breeding,
- replacement stock should be bought from as few as possible sources,
- isolation (quarantine) facility is a critical component of a PRRSV biosecurity program. Isolation facilities should be located more than 120 meters from the breeding herd and ideally, offsite. Incoming stock should be kept separately from the resident stock for a minimum of 30 days. Animals should be monitored daily for clinical signs by the farm personnel,
- replacement stock should be blood-tested 24-48 hours after the arrival to the isolation facility as well as 5-7 days prior to their entry to the breeding herd. Once infected, PRRSV RNA can be detected in the bloodstream 24 hours after the infection; therefore, testing of samples by PCR is recommended to enhance detection of per acute infections. Samples collected late in the isolation period can also be tested by ELISA for the presence of PRRSV antibodies,
- herd closure; interrupting the introduction of new pigs into the farm for at least 6 months (Torremorell and Christianson, 2002)
- semen for the artificial insemination must originate from the negative boars (Pitkin et al., 2011; Zimmerman et al., 2012).

2. Indirect routes

PRRSV can be mechanically transmitted in a number of ways:

- transport vehicles; PRRSV can be spread to susceptible animals following contact with contaminated transport vehicles. Therefore, as with facilities, stringent compliance with cleaning/disinfection and drying protocols is critical for sanitizing the trailers of transport vehicles. Following sanitation, the vehicle must be allowed adequate drying time after disinfection.

- around the farm the fence must be sited and the traffic in the yard must be banned. In front of each entry of farm buildings the disinfection footbaths must be placed (Dee et al., 2006; et al., 2011).
- visitors should be avoided as much as possible
- personnel and visitors; the hands, coveralls and boots of personnel can serve as mechanical vehicles for PRRSV. Personnel should practice one night of downtime before entering a farm. Research has shown that extended periods of downtime are not necessary for this agent. Shower protocols have been proven to successfully decontaminate personnel contaminated with PRRSV prior to entry. The use of such a procedure upon entry to the system each day is recommended. The Danish entry system; this system utilizes the changing of coveralls and boots plus the washing of hands in designated areas prior to entering the animal air space and has been demonstrated to be very effective for reducing the risk of PRRSV spread. Clothes and boots should never leave the farm and boots should be power-washed to remove feces from the soles and disinfected routinely (Dee et al., 2003; Otake et al., 2002; Pitkin et al., 2011).
- Insects; house flies and mosquitoes can serve as mechanical vectors of PRRSV and can transport the virus at least 2.4 km from an infected farm. In order to prevent spread of PRRSV via insects windows and areas that could be accessed by insects should be covered with screens. The use of insect bait is an effective means to control the number of insects. Cutting the grass and removing weeds surrounding swine facilities as well as removal of standing water are also recommended for eliminating insect breeding areas (Otake et al., 2003; Pitkin et al., 2009; Pitkin 2011).
- aerosol; airborne spread of PRRSV was established particularly at low temperature and high humidity (Dee et al., 2005; Otake et al., 2010; Pitkin et al., 2011).
- pig meat; meat from infected pigs can harbor PRRSV for at least 7 days at 4 °C and for months when frozen at -20 °C. Therefore, fresh or frozen pig meat should not be allowed into a swine facility at any time (Pitkin et al., 2011).

Internal biosecurity deals with the control of movement of virus from infected to non-infected animals within the same population. PRRS has tendency for self-recovery when biosecurity measures are implemented (Pitkin et al., 2011).

3. Direct transmission of virus

Direct transmission of virus could be prevented with:

- construction of pig facilities that allow that each pig category is in a separate room,
- swine facilities should be managed using all in, all out pig flow, thereby reducing the spread of PRRSV from older, infected pigs to younger, naïve animals,
- partial depopulation of critical category of pigs meaning to move weaners off-site,
- one way pig flow,
- **cross fostering** within 24 hours of birth,
- set up hospital pens in a separate room, even better choice is to euthanize animals with poor prospect of recovery. Moving these pigs to a remote area of the barn so that blood from the euthanasia process does not infect susceptible pigs,
- interrupting the introduction of own replacement females and males into the breeding herd for at least 6 months (Dee et al., 2003; Dee et al., 2006; Otake et al., 2002; Pitkin et al., 2009; Pitkin et al., 2011).

4. Indirect transmission of virus

Indirect transmission of virus could be prevented with:

- technology; all-in-all-out pig flow is an essential part of internal biosecurity. It is important to properly sanitize the facilities before introducing new animals. Otherwise the virus remains in the room and is important source of re-infection,
- categories of pigs must be separated by the different rooms,
- personnel's' and visitors' hands, coveralls and boots can serve as mechanical vehicles for PRRSV. Changing boots, clothes and gloves as well as strict hand disinfection is essential for preventing transfer of the virus between the buildings,
- use of footbaths can greatly help reducing the risk of PRRSV transfer between groups of pigs. Footbaths should be placed in front of each entry. Baths should be changed at least every day to maintain disinfectant efficacy,
- clean boots and changing coveralls after each category of pig,
- change disposable gloves between litters,
- change needles between sows and change needles between litters,
- equipment should be keep on-site otherwise equipment must be cleaned and disinfected,
- insects such as house flies and mosquitoes can serve as mechanical vectors of PRRSV. Therefore all inlets, windows and areas that could be accessed by insects should be covered with screens and the use of insecticides are highly recommended,
- regularly provide rodent control,
- any water supply that is drawn from a surface reservoir or shallow well can be a significant health risk. PRRS virus likes cold, wet conditions, and its survival in water is thought to be 10-14 days. That is why only clean and fresh water should be used,
- aerosol transmission is also a potential route of PRRSV spread between farms. For that purpose Air-filtration systems should be used (Dee et al., 2003; Dee et al., 2006; Otake et al., 2002; Pitkin et al., 2009; Pitkin et al., 2011).

The objective of this study was evaluation of implemented biosecurity measures on 24 farms with the intention of both the elimination of PRRS and general improvement of health status of farms.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Farms: The study was carried out from June 2010 till April 2014 on 24 farrow to finish farms.

Table 1. Number of breeding pigs and PRRS status for each farm.

Tabela 1. Broj priplodnih svinja i PRRS situacija za pojedine farme.

FARMS																								
Farm	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24
No. of breeding pigs	12	7	17	74	141	80	17	15	30	66	88	41	50	50	52	37	60	50	45	34	64	59	53	58
PRRS status before study	pos	neg	pos	pos	neg	neg	pos	neg	pos	pos														

Before study 4 farms were negative for antibodies against PRRSV (table 1).

Samplings procedure: Blood samples for blood analysis were collected from vena cava cranialis approximately every three months. Blood samples were collected into serum separator tubes (Vacuette, Greiner Bio-one, Kremsmunster, Austria). The tubes were left on a room temperature for 2 hours to clot prior to centrifugation at 1300 x g at 4 °C for 10 minutes.

All together 3962 blood samples were collected for serology.

Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA): The HerdChek, IDEXX Laboratories, PRRS X3 ELISA test was used for detecting antibodies in serum samples. The ELISA was performed according to the instructions of the manufacturer. The results of samples were divided in two groups, samples with S/P less than 0,4 as negative and samples with S/P greater than 0,4 as positive.

Detection of PRRSV with gel-based RT-PCR: Total RNA was extracted from 140 µl of serum samples using the QIAamp[®] viral RNA mini kit (Qiagen, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. 1837 samples were tested individually or as pools (maximum 5 samples in the pool) by one-step RT-PCR (One-Step RT-PCR Kit, Qiagen, Germany) using sequences based on the open reading frame 7 (ORF7), which detect Type 1 and Type 2 PRRSV strains respectively (Donadeu et al., 1999; Toplak et al., 2012). The PRRS strain VR-2332 (Type 2) and the Lelystad viruses (Type 1) were used as positive controls. Reaction mixtures without RNA served as a negative control.

Biosecurity measures: The owners got acquainted with the obligatory measures. The required biosecurity measures included the strict biosecurity protocols: herd closure (introducing of new pigs to the farm was prohibited for at least 200 days. In this period also gilts from the farm itself cannot enter the breeding herd), entering farm only after changing the clothes, for personnel changing of coveralls and boots, washing of hands, using footbaths, individual responsibility for each pig category, all in/all out system, one age category of pigs in one room, one way pig flow, cleaning and disinfection of pens, pig equipment kept on the farm, deratization and disinsection, new replacement or incoming stock should be negative, quarantine. With each visit (approximately every three months) we'd checked if owners implemented required biosecurity measures.

RESULTS

By ELISA and RT-PCR was proved that five of negative farms kept the negative status as a result of good biosecurity practice. From seven positive farms PRRS was eliminated (proved by ELISA and RT-PCR), all these farms adopted the strict biosecurity protocol and followed all the required biosecurity measures. In 12 farms they did not implement almost any of the required biosecurity measures. Besides other required biosecurity measures, the most important biosecurity measures that were not implemented are: the herd closure was not performed as well as all in/all out protocol, each pig category was not in a separate room, visitors and workers did not change the clothes and boots, a frequent traffic in the yard.

DISCUSSION

Preventing the introduction of disease agents is a continuous challenge for pork producers and veterinarians. When a farm or site is affected by a disease the impact

can be devastating to the health of swine and the producer's bottom line. Every farm or production system should have a written plan documenting its biosecurity protocols. Appropriate education, training and compliance strategies should be utilized so all people working on and around the farm are properly informed and trained to apply the required biosecurity measures. Personnel should review, understand and follow the applicable biosecurity protocols for their assigned tasks (Canadian Swine Health Board, 2010; Pitkin et al., 2011).

Five of the negative farms kept the negative status as a result of a good biosecurity practice. From seven positive farms PRRS was eliminated, all these farms adopted the strict biosecurity protocol. In 12 farms neither external nor internal biosecurity measures were implemented at all or at least not to a satisfying level.

One very important measure that was not followed was the all-in/all-out protocol. In consequence non-vacant pens could not be thoroughly cleaned and disinfected and this resulted in poor pen hygiene. It follows that both pigs and pens were the source of PRRSV. Moreover, additional staffs were not appointed to a single pig category and did not change coveralls or boots between pig categories, nor wash hands between pig categories. Hence these factors were the reason as well as the route of transmission of PRRSV between categories and between facilities. Pig equipment was not kept on the farm but rather brought to the farm without prior sterilization (tattooing pliers). From the results of serology, molecular testing and biosecurity measures, we can conclude that the owners did not follow the required biosecurity measures nor carried out a strict herd closure which all proved to be the reason for the unsuccessful elimination of PRRS from the farms. Therefore, strict biosecurity procedures have to be followed at all times and it is imperative to have isolation areas for all replacement animals (Torremorell and Christianson, 2002). In order to eliminate PRRS from the farm, the proposed measures should be strictly followed since we are dealing with a one-site farm. Farrow-to-finish farms are at a disadvantage when it comes to using herd closure and natural exposure procedure since virus infection from the grower animals cannot be kept away from the breeding herd (Torremorell and Christianson, 2002).

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the elimination with herd closure did not prove itself as a successful measure for elimination of PRRS from the 12 farrow-to-finish farm. Implementation of herd closure and biosecurity measures in field conditions is a much more difficult challenge than expected. Nonetheless, further study focusing on the education of farmers must be undertaken. On the other hand elimination of PRRS is possible even in situations in which neighboring farms are PRRS-positive and on one-site farms. Pig production in Slovenia is concentrated in few regions, so a regional program for elimination of PRRS is advisable to prevent the introduction of new viruses and to prevent movement of the virus within the farm and region (Štukelj, 2013).

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ZAŠTO ELIMINACIJA REPRODUKTIVNOG I RESPIRATORNOG SINDROMA (PRRS) SVINJA U SLOVENAČKIM UZGOJIMA SVINJA NIJE EFIKASNA?

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Izvod

Pre ulaska u Europsku zajednicu Slovenija bila je slobodna od Svinjskog reproduktivnog i respiratornog sindroma (PRRS) i za sve uvezene životinje obavezni su bili karantini. Prilikom ulaska Slovenije u EU naše granice postale su otvorene za uvoz živih životinja. Uvoznicima više ne treba predložiti iskaze o zdravstvenom stanju svinja. Prilikom nekontrolisanog uvoza u Sloveniju unose se različiti uzročnici bolesti. Već u drugoj polovini 2004 godine kod domaćih svinja prvi put smo utvrdili antitela protiv virusa PRRS. Proširenost PRRS u Sloveniji ponovo smo počeli istraživati tek 2010 godine u okviru monitoringa i 2011 godine u okviru zakonskog propisa o izvođenju sistematičkog praćenja stanja zaraznih bolesti i vakcinacija. U obe dve studije ustanovili smo 48 postotnu prevalenciju bolesti. U pozitivnim uzgojima ustanovili smo prisustvo virusa genotipa 1 sa mnogobrojnim podtipovima. U 2012. godini prvi put smo dokazali i viruse PRRS genotipa 2. Ovi podaci otkrivaju, kako se aljkavo izvode

karantini i kako se u uzgojima ne izvode ni najosnovnije mere biosigurnosti. U okviru uradene studije obradivali smo 24 uzgoja, kako bi ocenili izvođenje preventivnih mera protiv unosa bolesti. Pozitivnim uzgojima za eliminaciju bolesti predložili smo ili prirodno prekuženje ili izvođenje biosigurnosnih mera. Negativnim uzgajalištima predložili smo striktno izvođenje biosigurnosnih mera. Pet uzgoja, koje su bili u početku studije negativni uspeli su održati status, jer su izvodili sve propisane biosigurnosne mere. U sedam uzgoja smo u početku studije dokazali tako protivtela protiv virusa PRRS kako i virusnu nukleinsku kiselinu. U svih sedam uzgoja bolest smo eliminisali, jer su se odgajivači držali propisanih biosigurnosnih mera. U ostalim uzgojima ustanovili smo, da uopšte ne izvode ni vanjskih ni unutrašnjih biosigurnosnih mera ili jih izvode nedovoljno. Zbog toga se PRRS a možda i druge bolesti bezgranično šire između uzgoja i unutar njih. Glavni nedostaci, koje primećujemo u slovenačkim uzgojima su unos nove prasadi u uzgoj bez karantina, različite kategorije prasadi u istim prostorijama, neizvođenje sistema »all in, all out«, prodaja prasadi u dvorištu, mnogobrojne posete ljudi na farmi. Slovenija pre ulaska u EU nije bila dovoljno svesna svog visokog zdravstvenog stanja i nije dobila zvaničnog statusa zemlje proste PRRS, što bi značilo ekonomsku prednost. Bez planskog preduzimanja mera u smislu poboljšanja stanja prasadi se neće poboljšati ni stanje u svinjogojstvu.

Ključne reči: biosigurnosne mere, PRRS, kontrola.

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